

Automated Code Compliance Checks with BIM

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Abstract

Compliance checks are crucial for ensuring the quality, accuracy, and regulatory compliance of building design projects. However, the industry's current manual workflows for code compliance checks often result in time and money loss, re-work, and frustration. This study presents a mixed-approach research methodology to automate BIM compliance checks and address these challenges.

The methodology incorporates qualitative and quantitative methods and an applied research approach. The qualitative methods involve rule interpretation using classification and encoding systems and rule translation using the RASE (Requirements, Applicability, Selection, and Exception) Methodology and AI-language models. In contrast, the quantitative methods focus on model standardisation, visual programming, and Automated Code Compliance Check graphs.

The developed framework aims to automate compliance checks for general regulations and provide a practical solution for efficient and regulatory-compliant building design processes. The methodology is applied to a real-world case scenario, demonstrating its effectiveness in streamlining the compliance checking process.

The findings of this study contribute to the advancement of BIM-based compliance checking methodologies and offer practical insights for industry professionals. Ultimately, this

research seeks to improve the overall quality and effectiveness of building design projects by automating compliance checks in a seamless and adaptable manner.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/YtGyckLnNoQ>

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